

Research Paper

The Effect of Motivation and Communication on the Employee Achievement in the Office of Agriculture and Aceh Plantation

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of motivation and communication on work performed at the Aceh Agriculture and Plantation Office. The benefits of this study are to be able to provide a study of knowledge about the influence of motivation and communication on employee work performance for further research, to enrich scientific information, especially those related to motivation, communication and employee performance and as input for Aceh Agriculture and Plantation Office in making decisions for improving employee work performance by considering motivation and communication. The populations in this study were employees at the Office of Agriculture and Plantation of Aceh with a total of 430 employees so that the sample in this study amounted to 81 respondents; the authors used the Slovin formula as a tool to calculate sample size in this study. Simultaneous results of research on motivation and communication have a significant effect on employee work performance, said to be significant because F count 7.565 is greater than F table of 2.329. Partially the t value of the motivation variable has a significant effect on work performance because t arithmetic shows a number of 2.630 greater with a t table of 1.990. Partially the value of t count communication variable has a significant effect on work performance because t count shows a number of 3.778 greater than the value of t table of 1.990. The correlation coefficient (R) shows a value of 0.403 which indicates that the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable is positive because it has a value of $R > 0.5$. The R² value of 0.662 shows that only 66.2% of the variation of the dependent variable (work performance) can be explained by variations in the independent variables (motivation and communication) in this study. While the remaining 33.8% is explained by other variables that are not included in research that might affect work performance.

Keywords: Motivation, Communication and Work Achievement.

INTRODUCTION

Motivation is something that causes, channel, and supports human behavior so that they want to work hard and enthusiastically achieve optimal results. Motivation is a very important thing to be considered by the organization if you want each employee to contribute positively to the achievement of organizational goals

because the motivation of an employee will have a high enthusiasm in carrying out their duties and responsibilities. The importance of motivation because motivation is the thing that causes, channel, and supports human behavior so that they want to work hard and enthusiastically achieve optimal results. Because work motivation is a

driving factor or driving force for working for employees in an organization. ^[1]

Communication is also very important for the life of the organization. Communication is very important to establish cooperative relations between humans and organizations to help each other and conduct interactions. Communication plays an important role in establishing cooperation so that the organization can be achieved and has a very large influence in the process of achieving goals. Communication activities can affect internal activities including direction, giving orders, submitting reports in daily activities. While external communication activities are one of the activities between employees and parties outside the organization. The role of communication in an organization is very important. Communication within the organization serves to control employee behavior. Internal communication in organizations occurs in the scope of the organization, both upward, downward, and lateral communication. ^[2]

Communication is generally interpreted as a form of conveying information or messages and understanding from someone to others. Communication can succeed if there is a mutual understanding attitude from both parties between the sender of the message or information to the recipient of the message in order to understand each other. ^[3] Therefore the organization must provide a policy in the right work placement to support work performance. This is in accordance with the opinion of Hasibuan ^[4] that the proper placement of employees is one of the keys to obtaining optimal work performance from each employee. Job performance can be interpreted as the results achieved by a person according to the size that applies to the work in question. Because both the organization itself and employees need feedback on their respective efforts, therefore, it is necessary to assess employee performance. Job performance assessment is a formal process to periodically review and evaluate one's work performance. ^[5, 20] A

process is a systematic way or steps that are followed in producing something. The process of evaluating work performance is intended to understand one's work performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Humans as one of the main components in an organization must have a motivation that can spur to achieve what is desired. Managers must motivate employees towards performance that is expected to be able to meet the goals of an organization. Motivation comes from the Latin word "move" which means encouragement or movement. Motivation is a process that starts with a physiological or psychological definition that drives behavior or impulse aimed at intensive purposes. ^[6] Motivation is the desire found in individuals who stimulate them to take action. ^[4] Individual motivations with each other must be different and often change so that actions taken by one individual to another to achieve their desires are also different. This opinion is also the same according to Sutrisno ^[7, 1] that one's motives often experience change, because human desires always change according to their needs and interests.

Work motivation is nothing but something that raises enthusiasm or enthusiasm. ^[8] In short, work motivation is a driver of morale. Something here can come from within someone or outside of someone. Work motivation is the willingness to issue high-level efforts towards organizational goals, which are conditioned by the ability of efforts to meet individual needs. ^[9] The same thing was conveyed by Hamzah, ^[10] that work motivation is a process carried out to move a person so that his behavior can be directed at real efforts to achieve stated goals. Real efforts of one's work motivation will appear through: responsibility in carrying out work, accomplishments achieved, self-development, and independence in acting.

Organizations must have human resources to carry out their activities so that these activities can run well so those good

relationships are opened between members of the organization. The term communication comes from the Latin language "communicate" which means "tell". Whereas according to English is "common", from the basic word then becomes "communication" which means "an exchange of information, concepts, ideas, other feelings between parties two or more".^[11] Communication as a process of transferring information, ideas, understanding from someone to another person in the hope that others can interpret it according to the intended purpose.^[12]

Communication occurs when a source conveys a message to the recipient with an intention that is realized to influence the behavior of the recipient.^[13] The same opinion defines that communication is indeed very simple and easy to understand, but in its implementation, it is very difficult to understand, especially if those involved in communication have different references, or in one-way communication such as mass media, of course, to form this equation will experience a lot of constraints.^[14] Another opinion says that communication is the process of transferring understanding in the form of ideas or information from one person to another. The term work performance is often heard or very important for the organization to achieve its objectives. In the context of human resource development work performance.^[15]

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Population and Samples

The population is an area of generalization consisting of objects / subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics set by researchers to be studied and then drawn to conclusions.^[16] The populations in this study were employees at the Aceh Office of Agriculture and Plantation. With a total of 430 employees. While the sample is part of the population taken through certain ways that also have certain characteristics, clear and complete which are considered to represent

the population. The sample is part of the number and characteristics of the population. The sample was conducted because of the limitations of researchers in conducting research both in terms of funding, time, energy, and a very large population.^[16] Therefore, the sample taken must be truly representative (can represent). In determining the sample, the author uses the Slovin formula as a tool to calculate sample size because the population is known to be more than 100 respondents. To be clearer, here is the modified Slovin formula:^[17]

$$\text{Formula : } n = \frac{N}{1 + N e^2}$$

Where : n = Sample Size

N = Population Size

e = The error rate in this sampling is 10%

so the sample taken from the population is:

$$n = \frac{430}{1 + (430)(0,1^2)}$$
$$n = \frac{430}{5,3}$$
$$n = 81,13 = 81$$

Based on the understanding of population and sample, the sample in this study amounted to 81 respondents. Can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Respondents Profile

Respondents	Number of samples
General and Personnel Subdivisions	23
Sub Division of Finance and Assets	7
Field of Facilities and Infrastructure	9
Sub Division of Administration	13
Field of Food Crops	12
Extension Section	17

Data Analysis Technique

Descriptive Analysis is an analysis that describes the responses of respondents regarding supervision and work discipline to employee performance obtained from the results of respondents' answers.

The analytical model used in this study is a multiple linear regression model. Multiple linear regression analysis is an analysis tool that can be used to determine the effect of independent variables and

dependent variables, namely between. Motivation (X1), Communication (X2), and Work Achievement (Y) Look for the regression line equation using the formula: [18]

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

Y = Work performance
 α = Constants
X₁ = Motivation
X₂ = Communication
 β_1, β_2 = Regression Coefficient
e = Error

Validation and Reliability Testing

Before the research is carried out, the main step is to test the research instrument. The trials of the items on the two variables are intended to test the validity and reliability of the instrument items used in the study. For this reason, the results of the trials must be sought for validity and reliability.

Validation Testing

Validitas instrumen diuji menggunakan korelasi skor barang dengan skor total "Product Moment (Pearson)". [16] The analysis was performed on all items. The testing criteria were carried out by comparing r count with r table at the level of $\alpha = 0,05$. Product Moment correlation formula from Karl's Pearson: [16]

$$r_{xy} = \frac{n \sum xy - (\sum x \sum y)}{\sqrt{\{n \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2\} \{n \sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2\}}}$$

Information:

r_{xy} = The correlation coefficient between symptoms x and symptoms y
x = item item score
y = Total score
n = Amount of data +

If the result of the calculation turns out to be $r\text{-count} > r\text{ table}$ then the instrument item is considered valid, conversely if $r\text{ count} < r\text{ table}$ then it is considered invalid (invalid), so the instrument cannot be used in research. Meanwhile, correlation techniques to determine the validity of this item until now are the most widely used techniques: Furthermore, in giving interpretations of the

correlation coefficient, items that have a positive correlation with the criteria (total score) and correlation are high, indicating that the item has high validity. Usually, the minimum requirement that must be considered fulfilling the requirements is if $r = 0.3$. So if the correlation between items with a total score is less than 0.3, items in the instrument are declared invalid. [16]

Reliability Testing

The instrument reliability coefficient is intended to see the consistency of the answers to the statements given by the respondent. The analysis tool uses the split method by correlating the odd total score and even the total score, then the reliability is calculated using the "Spearman-Brown" formula: [16]

$$r_i = \frac{2r_b}{1 + r_b}$$

Information:

r_i = internal reliability of all instruments
 r_b = Product Moment Correlation between the first and second hemispheres

Giving interpretation of reliability (r_1) is generally used as a benchmark as follows: [16]

Reliability (r_1) the trial is equal to or more than 0.70 which means that the test results have high reliability.

Reliability (r_1) of a trial of less than 0.70 means the results of the test run have unreliable reliability.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Characteristics of Respondents

The number of respondents in this study was 430 people, the authors used the Slovin formula as a tool to calculate the sample size at the Office of the Agriculture and Plantation Office of Aceh, which was 81 respondents. Of the 81 questionnaires that were circulated, everything was completely filled in as needed, so that a number of the questionnaires were analyzed. The characteristics of the respondents referred to in this study consisted of gender, education, the age of the respondent and marital status. To find out how the

composition of the respondent's characteristics is based on the criteria above, it will be presented in the form of a table of

respondents' frequency distribution and an explanation regarding the table 2.

Table 2. Recapitulation of Respondents' Response to Motivation at the Aceh Agriculture and Plantation Office.

Motivation Indicator	total	Assessment
I am fully responsible for my work	331	Well
Before carrying out a job, I first determine the target of implementation	336	Well
In my work, I always try to outperform my colleagues	342	Well
I create new things to improve the success of the task	342	Well
I try to work hard to achieve the best performance at work	321	Well
Total number	1,672	Very good
Average	334,4	Very good

Based on Table 2, the results of respondents' assessment of Motivation at the Office of Agriculture and Plantation of Aceh with a total score of 1672 were obtained. From these results, it can be said that the respondents responded very well to the motivation at the Aceh Agriculture and Plantation Office.

Table 3. Recapitulation of Respondent's Response to Communication at the Aceh Agriculture and Plantation Office.

Communication Indicator	Total	Assessment
Mr / Ms did not experience difficulties in communicating with the leadership	336	Well
All tasks and orders arrive at each employee	305	Well
You can communicate with leaders through formal communication media	345	Well
You can communicate with leaders through informal communication media	325	Well
Mr / Ms make formal communication with the leadership regularly	382	Well
Total Number	1,693	Very good
Average	338,6	Very good

Source: primary data processed, 2018.

Based on Table 3, the results obtained from respondents' assessment of leadership communication at the Aceh Agriculture and Plantation Office with a total score of 1693. From these results, it can be said that the respondents responded very well to communication at the Aceh Agriculture and Plantation Office.

Table 4. Recapitulation of Respondents' Response to Work Achievement at the Aceh Agriculture and Plantation Office

Job Performance Indicators	Total	Assessment
In an effort to improve my work performance, the management carried out a fair assessment process	329	Well
The assessment of work performance carried out for me is in accordance with the reality that happened	363	Well
The results of the assessment carried out to me are in accordance with the work performance that has been produced by me, not because of the closeness of the relationship between me and the leader	345	Well
The results of a transparent work performance assessment will improve my ability to work in the future	328	Well
The results of the work performance evaluation can be trusted	357	Well
Total Number	1,722	Very good
Average	344,4	Very good

Source: primary data processed, 2018

Based on Table 4, the results obtained from respondents' assessment of work performed at the Aceh Agriculture and Plantation Office with a total score of 1,722. From these results, it can be said that the respondents responded very well to work performed at the Aceh Agriculture and Plantation Office.

Multicollinearity Test Results

The multicollinearity test was conducted to test whether the regression

model found a correlation between the independent variables. [19] The symptoms of multicollinearity can be seen from tolerance value or the value of Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). The tolerance value limit is 0.1 and the VIF limit is 10. If the tolerance value is <0.1 or VIF > 10 = multicollinearity occurs. If the tolerance value is > 0.1 or VIF < 10 = there is no multicollinearity. The results of testing on multicollinearity in this study can be seen in table 5.

Table 5. Multicollinearity Test Results

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	11.252	3.998		2.815	.006		
	Motivation	.110	.174	.065	2.630	.530	.994	1.006
	Communication	.355	.094	.393	3.778	.000	.994	1.006

Source: primary data processed, 2018

Based on table 5 above, it can be seen that no independent variable has a VIF value greater than 10 and no one has a tolerance value smaller than 0.1. So it can be concluded that this study is free from multicollinearity. From the results of the analysis, the VIF value of the motivation variable is 1.006 (<10) and the tolerance value is 0.994 (> 0.1), the VIF value of the communication variable is 1.006 (<10) and the tolerance value is 0.994 (> 0.1). Thus it can be concluded that the independent variables used in this study passed the test for symptoms of multicollinearity.

Analysis of Multiple Linear Regression

Multiple linear regression analysis is used to measure the influence of independent variables on the dependent variable and predict the dependent variable using independent variables. In this case to find out the influence of motivation and communication on work performed at the Aceh Agriculture and Plantation Office. The output from the IBM SPSS Statistics 22 program has obtained regression values as shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Regression

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.		
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	11.252	3.998		2.815	.006		
	Motivation	.110	.174	.065	2.630	.530	.994	1.006
	Communication	.355	.094	.393	3.778	.000	.994	1.006

Source: primary data processed, 2018

Obtained:

$$a = 11,252$$

$$b1 = 0,110$$

$$b2 = 0,355$$

The regression equation model can be obtained:

$$Y = 11,252 + 0,110 + 0,355 + e$$

DISCUSSION

From multiple linear regression analysis, it can be seen that the constant value is 11.252. This value indicates that when motivation is zero, then work performance (Y) will be worth 11.252. While the value of X1 which is equal to 0.110 shows that when there is an increase in motivation of one unit, the work performance will increase by 0.110 units. Then if the value of X2 which is equal to 0.355 shows that when there is an increase in the communication of one unit, then the work performance will increase by 0.355 units. Thus the higher the influence of

motivation and communication, the more significant it will affect work performance at the Aceh Agriculture and Plantation Office.

The relationship between the two variables (simultaneous) motivation and communication has a significant effect on employee work performance, said to be significant because Fcount 7.565 is greater than Ftable 2.329. So Ha = accepted and Ho = rejected. It can be concluded that the hypothesis proposed is alleged motivation and communication has a positive relationship with employee performance proven truth.

Partially the t-count of the motivation variable (X1) has a significant effect on performance because t-count shows the number 2,630 is greater with the t-table value at the 5 percent confidence level indicating the number 1,990. So Ha = accepted and Ho = rejected. It can be concluded that the hypothesis proposed is

that alleged motivation has a positive relationship with work performance proven to be correct. Partially the value of the communication variable (X2) has a significant effect on performance because t-count shows the number 3.778 is greater than the t-table value at the 5 percent confidence level which shows the number 1.990. So H_a = accepted and H_o = rejected. It can be concluded that the hypothesis proposed is that it is suspected that communication has a positive relationship with a performance that is proven to be true.

The correlation coefficient (R) shows a value of 0.403 which indicates that the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable is positive because it has a value of $R > 0.5$. The value of R^2 0.662 shows that only 66.2% of the variation of the dependent variable (work performance) can be explained by variations in the independent variables (motivation and communication) in this study. While the remaining 33.8% is explained by other variables that are not included in the study that can affect performance.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion described earlier, some conclusions can be drawn as follows:

- 1) Simultaneously motivation and communication have a significant effect on employee work performance, said to be significant because F-count 7.565 is greater than F-table of 2.329. Thus H_a = accepted and H_o = rejected.
- 2) It can be concluded that the hypothesis proposed is alleged motivation and communication have a positive relationship with the work performance of employees proven the truth.
- 3) Partially the t-count value of the motivation variable (X1) has a significant effect on work performance because t-count shows a number of 2.630 greater with t-table of 1.990. Thus H_a = accepted and H_o = rejected. It can be concluded that the hypothesis

proposed is that alleged motivation has a positive relationship with work performance proven to be true.

- 4) Partially the value of the calculation variable communication (X2) has a significant effect on work performance because t-count shows a number of 3.778 greater than the value of t table of 1.990. Thus H_a = accepted and H_o = rejected. It can be concluded that the hypothesis proposed is that it is suspected that communication has a positive relationship with work performance proven to be true. The correlation coefficient (R) shows a value of 0.403 which indicates that the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable is positive because it has a value of $R > 0.5$. The R^2 value of 0.662 shows that only 66.2% of the variation of the dependent variable (work performance) can be explained by variations in the independent variables (motivation and communication) in this study. While the remaining 33.8% is explained by other variables that are not included in research that might affect work performance.

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